

Corrigendum to “Energy consistent framework for continuously evolving 3D crack propagation” [Comput. Methods Appl. Mech. Engrg. 324 (2017) 54–73]

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Abstract

This corrigendum aims to correct errors in the graphs axes ranges resulting from miss-scaling of the results.

Keywords:

brittle fracture, configurational forces, crack tracking, mesh smoothing

We regret that the aforementioned paper contained erroneously presented results. The correction given here does not affect the presented numerical framework nor does change the conclusions or outcomes of the article. Numerical analysis and numerical results remain the same. Correct presentation of the results addressing post-processing mistakes in Figures 8, 12 and 15 of the original article is given below.

More precisely, the vertical axis in Figure 8 a) should be scaled by 10^{-2} rather than not scaled at all, and the displacement at the horizontal axis in Figure 8 b) should be divided not only by the varying load factor (as was done in the original paper), but also by the applied force according to the formula presented in the text of Section 8.1 that is $u = 2\Psi/(\tau f)$.

Furthermore, the horizontal axis in Figures 12 b) and Figure 12 c) should be scaled by 10^{-2} and, similarly to the results of Figure 8, the denominator used was only the load factor which was not multiplied by the applied force of 100 [N].

Finally, the vertical axis in Figure 15 a) should be scaled by a factor of 10^{-3} rather than 10^{-4} and the horizontal axis in Figure 15 b) should be scaled by 10/3, which results from the wrong scaling of the elastic energy and the missing scaling of the force in the denominator.

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Figure 8: Energy versus crack area and load versus displacement plots for graphite cylinder slice test.

Figure 12: Elastic energy versus crack area and force versus displacement plots for 1st-, 2nd- and 3rd-order of approximation and various initial crack inclinations for mixed mode loading example.

Figure 15: (a) Elastic energy versus crack area and (b) load versus displacement plots for torsion test.